

Modified Blower-Vac apparatus for sampling invertebrate communities. Arrows indicate the flow of air, water, and invertebrates through the apparatus. (n) = new, (m) = modified part from the original Blower-Vac.

water trap, fix the unit firmly to the blower. A PVC reducer (measuring 10 cm high and 5.8 cm in diam) attached to the blower base facilitates a stronger vacuum than the original model.

The modified version uses the same sampling enclosure as the earlier one (45-cm-diam plastic bucket with its bottom removed and top-fitted with a 1-m-long muslin / fiberglass net). An additional muslin sleeve can also be attached to the top netting to provide a side access. Arthropods inside the enclosure are sampled in a downward spiral beginning with the muslin netting, followed by the air column and the water column and soil. Because arthropod populations in rice increase in both species richness and abundance with crop age (at least up to maximum tillering), sampling time should also increase.

Vacuum tests of the original and modified Blower-Vac machines.

Model	Time trial ^a			Av
	T1	T2	T3	
Original	27	23	23	24.3
Modified	18	18	19	18.3

^aTime (in s) required to fill the water trap.

Vacuum tests revealed a more powerful vacuum in the modified than in the original model (see table); additional vacuum in the modified version allows easier capture of large invertebrates (e.g., rice bugs) inside the enclosure. A comparison of arthropod catches in the modified Blower-Vac, FARMCOP, D-vac, and sweep net methods is in progress and will be published at a later date. Interested readers, however, can consult the table in Arida and Heong (1992) that

compared arthropod catches from two D-vac models (backpack and hand-carried), FARMCOP, and the original Blower-Vac. Because the modified Blower-Vac catches more larger sized invertebrates than the original model, the modified method is expected to representatively sample a wider range of species than the original method.

The addition of a vial caddy and the attachment of a tripod to the blower unit (see figure) allows 2-3 persons to comfortably operate the unit. The materials and the machine blower unit cost approximately US\$150, comparable in price to the original model reported in 1992 (\$158). For safe operation, we recommend using an aspirator mask, earplugs, and goggles.

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A new Senegalese thresher/cleaner responds to small-farmer postharvest needs

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Development agents cite harvest and postharvest constraints as major factors in the profitability of irrigated rice production in the Senegal River Valley. Existing systems are expensive, too time-consuming, or too labor-intensive during periods of peak labor demand. An IRRI technology exchange with WARDA has provided a potential solution.

WARDA and its partners, with the help of an IRRI agricultural engineer and Senegalese expertise, developed a Senegalese prototype of the IRRI-designed TC800 axial flow thresher/cleaner. Here we report on the adaptations made, and the technical and financial performance. In an accompanying article (Donovan et al, page 41), we report on the collaborative

Table 1. Key adjustments to the original TC800 thresher-cleaner from IRRI for the Senegalese ASI prototype, under guidance from the ADRAO-SAED-ISRA engineering team.

Wheels fitted
Ability to pull the machine by animal power added
All housing assemblies fortified
Security added to protect hands while feeding straw into the machine
Blower enlarged (almost twice as large)
Air entry to blower made adjustable
Feed tray enlarged
Number of discharge louvers increased from 5 to 6
Two oscillating screens installed instead of one
All shaft diameters enlarged
Rings stabilizing oscillating screens modified to include ball bearings to reduce wear and tear
Larger threshing cylinder assembly strengthened and enlarged; diameter increased from 270 to 445 mm and length from 600 to 885 mm
Length of peg teeth in threshing cylinder enlarged from 100 to 150 mm
U-beam assembly added to eccentric arm to strengthen and stabilize it
Installation of alternating rows with 8 or 9 peg teeth instead of 5
Straw exit in front of machine made adjustable
Exit for immature and damaged grains brought to opposite side of the machine
Auger discharge spout enlarged from 80 to 100 mm
Grain auger assembly: distance between auger flights enlarged from 56 to 100 mm
12-hp diesel engine added

Table 2. Financial comparison of ASI and Votex machines.

	ASI	Votex
Technical and financial parameters		
Type of machine	Axial flow	Tangential flow
Grain separation rate (% of rough rice)	97.99	85
Daily processing capacity (kg d ⁻¹)	6,000	4,300
Days worked yr ⁻¹	55	55
Hours worked d ⁻¹	6.00	6.00
Rough rice price (US\$)	0.17	0.17
Charge for processing services (% of rough rice)	10	8
Purchase price (US\$)	4,138	3,276
Fuel consumption (L h ⁻¹)	2.0	0.8
Workers needed: operators	2	1
laborers (provided by farmers)	4	4
Exchange rate (CFA francs US\$ ⁻¹)	580	580
Financial results (in US\$)		
Fixed costs (annual)		
Depreciation, interest	1,522	1,228
Maintenance and repairs	414	328
Taxes, insurance, etc.	20.69	16.38
Total fixed costs yr ⁻¹	1,986	1,572
Total fixed costs t ⁻¹	6.02	6.65
Variable costs (annual)		
Fuel and oil	679	442
Labor	379	190
Total variable costs yr ⁻¹	1,058	632
Total variable costs t ⁻¹	3.21	2.67
Total costs yr ⁻¹	3,044	2,204
Total costs ha ⁻¹	41.51	41.94
Total costs t ⁻¹	9.23	9.32
Gross revenues t ⁻¹	17.24	13.79
Gross revenues yr ⁻¹	5,690	3,262
Net revenues t ⁻¹	8.02	4.47
Net revenues yr ⁻¹	2,645	1,058
Breakeven tonnage (annual) (t yr ⁻¹)	142	141
Breakeven workdays (d yr ⁻¹)	23.7	32.8
Debt repayment (yr)	1.0	1.8
Net present value	10,780	4,047
Internal financial rate of return (%)	65.6	34.1
Benefit/cost ratio	1.7	1.4

Source: Donovan C, Douthwaite B. 1997. Financial analysis of the ASI (thresher/cleaner). WARDA, St. Louis, Senegal. (mimeo.)

effort that was critical in producing the Senegalese thresher / cleaner, which was named ASI.

In 1995, research in the region indicated many problems with current harvest and postharvest technology. Combine harvesters were aging rapidly and were not being replaced. The 1994 devaluation of the regional currency, the CFA franc, increased the cost of imported equipment and spare parts. Plot-level surveys in 1994-95 show harvesting dates as much as 2 mo past maturity because farmers waited for combine harvesters. Therefore, many farmers shifted to manual harvest and threshing. But, manual methods are difficult and time-consuming, and extend the period of exposure of rice crop to hot, dry Sahelian winds.

The Votex thresher was introduced into the region during the early 1990s. Machine components for the Votex are imported for assembly, rather than built in the region. The Votex requires 5 or 6 people to operate the machine efficiently for threshing, with an 85% separation rate. Another 6-9 laborers are then needed to sift the straw manually to recover the remaining 15%, as well as to winnow and clean the threshed rice before bagging. In a 1994 survey, farmers complained that the performance of the Votex was insufficient and the labor requirements too high.

In 1995, IRRI donated two stripper / gatherer (SG) systems, with the SG800 stripper / harvester and the TC800 thresher / cleaner, to WARDA for evaluation in West African irrigated rice conditions. Testing of the TC800 in Senegal showed that the machine needed adjustments. For example, the feed tray and blower were too small to handle manually harvested rice, and the machine was too fragile overall. There were no wheels to maneuver the machine in the fields or allow animal-drawn transport. Table 1 lists the major modifications undertaken during the 2 1/2 yr of product development.

The performance characteristics and financial analysis of the ASI are given in

Table 2, including a comparison with results of the Votex thresher operating under similar conditions. The parameters were chosen to be realistic assessments in the Senegalese context, based on earlier trials and current work. With a 12-hp diesel motor and 6 workers, the ASI yields 6,000 kg d⁻¹ of clean rice from manually harvested production in fields with yields of approximately 4.5 t ha⁻¹. Under similar operating conditions, the Votex capacity is 4,300 kg d⁻¹. The separation recovery rate was 99% in on-farm tests for the ASI, much higher than the Votex's 85%. Thus, with the ASI, total labor needed is 6 workers. No additional labor is needed for sifting the straw for unthreshed rice or for winnowing, because of the efficient separation of rice from straw. Daily perform-

ance for both machines depends on the relative grain to straw proportion, the grain yield, the moisture content of the straw, and the speed of input of harvested crop.

The financial analysis evaluates the profitability of the machine for a service operator in order to assess potential distribution. With a purchase price of US\$4,138 and the parameters in Table 2, the cost per ton for the ASI is US\$9.23, when operator labor is the only labor included (the current system). For the Votex, per-ton costs are only slightly higher (\$9.32). The ASI's net revenues are more than double the revenues for the Votex, primarily because of the higher processing rate. ASI's benefit-cost ratio of 1.7 is in the acceptable range for investments, even with only 55 workdays yr⁻¹.

In addition to revenues for the ASI owner, farmers also benefit. The ASI has a high quality of output and reduces the time for postharvest work. This in turn lowers postharvest grain losses that arise from delays and loss of humidity. Labor for winnowing, cleaning, and sifting, which is usually supplied by the farm household, is no longer needed. The modified ASI helps reduce calendar constraints to double cropping, avoid grain losses from delays, reduce total harvest and post-harvest costs, and provide local employment in artisan workshops and agroindustry. In terms of demand, SISMAR, the local manufacturer of the ASI, is unable to meet current demand for the machine. ■

Technology transfer from Asia to Africa sets the stage for public- and private-sector collaboration in new technology in Senegal

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In the early 1990s, the productivity and profitability of irrigated systems in the Senegal River Valley began to be questioned. The Senegal River Valley Development Authority (known as SAED) found that harvest and postharvest constraints were very important, both in costs and in grain quality losses. SAED agents therefore turned to research, specifically to the Senegalese Agricultural Research Institute (known by the French acronym ISRA) and to WARDA to help find alternatives.

In response to WARDA's request, IRRI donated prototypes of the TC800 axial flow thresher/cleaner and the SG800 stripper gatherer. WARDA and ISRA modified the TC800, with help from SAED, a local artisan, farmers, and local agro-industry. By November 1997, a new thresher/cleaner, known as the ASI, was released in Senegal. A

companion article by Wopereis et al, page 39, presents the technical and financial results. Here, we present the development process of the ASI, an example of how research, development, private industry, and farmers can work together to meet technology needs.

IRRI researchers developed the SG800 and the TC800 to meet the needs of small-scale Asian rice farmers. Early in 1995, with the IRRI-donated prototypes and construction plans, IRRI and WARDA collaborated with SAED and ISRA to assess the potential of the machines in Sahelian irrigated rice production systems. In November 1995, during the wet-season harvest, an IRRI agricultural engineer (B. Douthwaite) assisted technicians and machinists with field tests of the machines. These people developed a list of changes recommended to strengthen the machine and adapt it, particularly for use with manually harvested fields and under wet field conditions. A workshop was organized with the major stakeholders involved, including farmers, rice millers, local manufacturers, representatives from the development agencies (SAED, etc.), researchers from WARDA and ISRA,

and extension agents, to discuss test results and future work.

WARDA, SAED, and ISRA decided to work with a local artisan skilled with agricultural machinery in order to build a Senegalese prototype, using the existing TC800 model and the IRRI plans. One of the challenges was to build the machines with locally available materials. The artisan chosen was skilled with agricultural machinery (including the existing Votex thresher), and his machine shop was sufficiently (and typically) equipped. By the dry season of 1996-97, testing of the new local prototype took place in farmers' fields as well as on WARDA's research farms, with the IRRI engineer again assisting. Farmers participated in the equipment tests, indicating areas of concern with the design and operation. The advantage of using both local materials and local expertise was evident during the tests. Alternatives could be tested and minor changes made rapidly in the field or in the nearby artisan workshop, without major time delays. Thus, local artisans are in a good position to build, maintain, and repair the machines in the future.